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RESEARCH OF THE INTERACTION OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP AS A TOOL OF DEVELOPMENT OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY

Об'єктом дослідження є державно-приватне партнерство (ДПП) як інструмент стратегічного управління розвитком альтернативної енергетики. Одним з найбільш проблемних місць є виявлення та ідентифікація функцій, напрямів та шляхів взаємодії ДПП. Програмно-цільовий метод дослідження, наряду з іншими використаними методами, дозволяє визначити пріоритетні напрями ефективності взаємодії ДПП як інструменту стратегічного управління розвитком альтернативної енергетики. А також здійснити вибір організаційних шляхів розвитку ДПП та сформулювати концепцію ДПП. В ході дослідження використовувалися методи системно-структурного, просторового аналізу, логічного узагальнення, синтезу, порівняння, індукції та дедуції, за допомогою яких проведено попередній аналіз формування проблеми, визначення цілей. Визначено сутність понять «державно-приватне партнерство», «партнерство», досліджено автономні державні функції. Визначено характеристики щодо переваг партнерів від участі в спільних проектах з використанням методу аналогій та порівняльного співставлення. Отримано визначення напрямів регулювання партнерських відносин з боку держсектору. Це пов'язано з тим, що запропонований метод має ряд особливостей, які складаються в розробленні стратегії та принципів побудови стосунків взаємодії, сприянні формуванню ефективного інституційного середовища та опрацюванні державою форм, методів та конкретних механізмів взаємодії ДПП. Визначено організаційні шляхи розвитку ДПП як інструмента стратегічного управління розвитком альтернативної енергетики, які зазначають, що участь держсектору поширюється до рівня отримання блокуючої меншості. У такий спосіб держава має достатню міру впливу. Завдяки цьому забезпечується можливість своєчасного, правильного та умілого використання визначених функцій, напрямів та шляхів взаємодії ДПП як інструмента стратегічного управління розвитком альтернативної енергетики. Це забезпечує активізацію інноваційної та інвестиційної діяльності і в найкоротші терміни досягнення сприятливих економічних показників в енергетичній галузі, як на рівні окремих регіонів, так і держави в цілому, що сприяє стійкому розвитку економіки країни.

Ключові слова: державно-приватне партнерство, розвиток економіки країни, інструмент стратегічного управління, суверенні функції держави.

1. Introduction

The interaction of the private sector and the state in solving important public problems has a rather long history, including in Ukraine. However, the possibility of using public-private partnerships (PPP) in the creation of alternative energy facilities has been considered relatively recently. In this connection, in Ukraine, the partnership between the state and business has become particularly relevant in recent years. This can be explained by several reasons. First, the complications of social, economic life make it difficult for the state to perform socially significant functions. Secondly, the private sector today is extremely interested in new efficient investment projects. And, thirdly, only by joint efforts of the state and the private sector of the economy can stimulate the creation of new innovative objects of alternative energy, implement large economic and social-ecological important projects. And also to increase the investment attractiveness of many complex projects in the strategically important energy industry. As practice shows, the effectiveness of these projects is different, which necessitates studying the problems of developing the inter-

action of PPP and increasing the efficiency of managing projects that affect the development of alternative energy. The PPP topic has a small research experience. The topic focuses on the problems associated with the definition of the PPP essence, the mechanism of its functioning and the areas of implementation [1–3]. The regional focus of the PPP development has many problems and is widely discussed [4–6]. Of great interest is the study of PPP problems in the administrative and legal aspect [7, 8]. And also in the distribution of risks of participants of PPP and investment component [9, 10]. At the same time, the works mainly reflect the organizational, legal and economic aspects of this mechanism. Issues related to the interaction of PPP in alternative energy remain poorly studied. Scientific understanding requires the problem of determining the PPP optimal concept as a tool for strategic management of the development of alternative energy. So, *the object of research* is PPP as a tool for strategic management of the development of alternative energy. And *the aim of research* is substantiation of the PPP interaction as a tool for strategic management of the development of alternative energy.

2. Methods of research

The research methodology is based on the following scientific methods:

- system-structural, spatial analysis, logical generalization, synthesis, comparison, induction and deduction – for preliminary analysis with the problem statement, the definition of goals. As well as to define the essence of the concepts «public-private partnership», «partnership» and for the study of autonomous functions;
- tabular and graphical methods – to visualize the research results;
- analogies and comparative comparisons – to characterize the relative advantages of partners (the state and the private sector) from participation in joint projects;
- program-target method – to determine the priority directions of the effectiveness of the interaction of PPP as a tool for the strategic management of the development of alternative energy and to develop areas for regulating partnerships. And also to choose the organizational paths for the development of public-private partnerships and to formulate the PPP concept.

3. Research results and discussion

The most important priority areas are:

- development of a methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of public-private partnership projects in order to determine ways of increasing the economic return of infrastructure projects (which today are implemented by the state only with the participation of private capital);
- establishment of barriers to their development and the determination of conditions conducive to improving the efficiency of such interaction, which leads to an increase in the innovative activity of project participants and an acceleration of the pace of territorial innovation development. And also contributes to the continuous innovative development of alternative energy.

Public-private partnership by its economic nature is the result of the development of economic relations between the state (local) government and the private sector for the development, planning, financing, construction and operation of primarily socially significant facilities [11, 12]. The fundamentally new sovereign functions of the state that should be implemented at a qualitatively new level are connected with PPP. And in this case it is important to pay attention to two aspects that are interrelated. First of all, partnership projects in the strategic management of the development of alternative energy contribute to some view the essence of the concept of autonomous functions. The second point is the narrowing of the circle of permanent public interests, their structural transformation, probably the emergence of new sharply raised questions, the extent to which the state is ready to give up its sovereign functions in favor of the private sector. As

a carrier of public functions, the public sector in partnership performs certain functions in the following sequence (Fig. 1).

Regulation of partnerships on the part of the public sector should be carried out in three areas:

- 1) the state should develop a strategy and principles, on the basis of which the relations of partners will be built both among themselves and of each of them with the society, it is necessary to fix it in official documents;
- 2) the public sector should contribute to the formation of an effective institutional environment, since without it, the achievement of high performance for projects is impossible;
- 3) the state organizes and manages the PPP, develops its forms, methods and specific mechanisms.

The functions of control and regulation of partnership projects by the state can be carried out by specialized ministries and departments or specially authorized bodies. At the same time, special bodies can be created for sectors of the economy where partnership agreements are mainly used (as is the case in Poland, where there are relevant institutions for roads, electric power industry, railways). It is also possible to create a single body uniting all or most of the branches (the practice of Serbia).

From an organizational point of view, a partnership as a tool for the strategic management of alternative energy development can develop in two ways:

- 1) the public sector and private business representatives may join the existing enterprise or jointly create a mixed company. The main principle of PPP is the pooling of public and private sector investments. The participation of the public sector extends to the level of obtaining a blocking minority, thus the state has a sufficient degree of influence. But this is not possible everywhere, because, for example, French law suggests that the public sector be the owner of most of the assets;
- 2) the partners sign an agreement – this can be a cooperation agreement, an agreement to manage the company, an agreement on implementation, assignment, leasing, that is, one of the modern forms of PPP.

As for the role of the private partner in joint projects, its main contribution is, above all, professional experience, effective management, advanced technology, harmonious institutional environment, flexibility and efficiency of decision making, ability to innovate and, of course, money.

Fig. 1. Diagram of the sequence of performance of public sector functions in the implementation of partnerships in alternative energy

The main state contribution is property, tax preferences, legal guarantees for private business representatives, financial resources.

Both partners benefit from participation in joint projects, while gaining certain advantages (Table 1).

Table 1

Advantages of partners from participation in joint projects

State benefits	Private sector benefits
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – increased budget and socio-ecological – economic efficiency of the implementation of partnership projects; – private investments are attracted to create elements of the innovation infrastructure, in particular, alternative energy facilities; – reduced socio-economic risks in the implementation of large investment projects; – provides rapid infrastructure development and the possibility of providing services of higher quality; – attracts not only the funds of a private partner, but also his professional experience, as well as experience in the field of investment and innovation; – reduced budget expenditures for project implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – new investment opportunities and, accordingly, new sources of income; – state protectionism and assistance in the implementation of infrastructure projects with high expected results and numerous risks; – state guarantees for investment projects and their co-financing; – possibility of obtaining subsidies for long-term investment; – equity participation and, accordingly, equity responsibility for the implementation of the PPP project; – opportunities for dialogue with the Government

PPP concept in its economic content represents the deep development of sustainable tools for the economic interaction of the public sector with the private sector in the design, planning and financing of partner projects, including the use of infrastructure facilities. The authorities often reserve the right to dispose of, and the authority to own and use the created property, as well as the functions of administrative and economic management, are delegated by representatives of private business. Partnership is a symbiosis, as a result of which the state and the private sector realize their capabilities and resources. In particular, the key activity of the public sector is the implementation of services in accordance with strategic priorities.

4. Conclusions

In contrast to the views that have been gained so far, the scientists who considered the PPP essence as a result of the development of economic interrelations between the government and the private sector have proposed a different approach. Namely, to consider PPP as a concept of constant tools for the economic interaction of the public sector with the private from the standpoint of the development of alternative energy. The development of alternative energy is reflected in the principles of sustainability, providing for the satisfaction of current and future ge-

nerations and the reproduction of all types of resources. It is noted that the PPP interaction as a tool for the strategic management of the development of alternative energy activates innovative and investment activities. It will also allow achieving favorable economic indicators in the energy sector, both at the level of individual regions and the state as a whole, which will contribute to the sustainable development of the country's economy. Research results will be useful as a promising model of the organization of interaction between government and business for the implementation of significant projects in the field of alternative energy.

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